

1 **TCF7, TCF7L1, and Lef1 together with TCF21 and TCF15 define a basic TCF requirement in the TE**
2 **lineage specification program.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe a specific requirement
9 for TCF lineage factors in lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo. TCF15 and
10 TCF21 exerted unique control of trophectoderm fate choice dynamics.

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